

European Cloud for Heritage Open Science

Deliverable D1.2 Ethics and Data Management Plan

HORIZON-CL2-2023-HERITAGE-ECCCH-01

Horizon Innovation action

Authors: Paolo Cignoni (CNR)

Project start	1 June 2024
Project duration	60 months
Document Identifier	10.5281/zenodo.17513615

**Funded by
the European Union**

**UK Research
and Innovation**

ECHOES is a project funded by the European Commission under Grant Agreement n.101157364, with the support of UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee n.10110142 & n.10110466.

© 2025 by the authors, the ECHOES consortium. This work is licensed under a "CC BY 4.0" license.

Deliverable Information

Project Number	101157364	Acronym	ECHOES
Full title	European Cloud for Heritage OpEn Science		
Project URL	https://www.echoes-ecch.eu/		
EU Project Officer	Christian WILK		

Deliverable	D1.2	Title	Ethics and Data Management Plan
Work Package	WP1	Title	Project Management
Submission date	22/01/2025		
Pages	14	Keywords	Data Management, Data Protection, Project Data

Lead Partner	CNR
Responsible Author	Paolo CIGNONI (CNR)
Authors (Partner)	Paolo Cignoni, Eliana Siotto, Marco Potenziani (CNR)
Contributors	Dimitris Kotzinos (CNRS-CYU), Carlos Andujar (UPC), Léna Czech, Areti Damala, Xavier Rodier (CNRS)

Change log

Date	Version	Author	Change
01/12/24	V0.1	Paolo Cignoni	First Draft based on the EU template
19/12/24	V0.2	Paolo Cignoni, Eliana Siotto	First draft submitted to the Steering Committee
20/12/24	V0.3	Dimitris Kotzinos, Carlos Andujar	Comments and proposition of new structure
09/01/25	V0.4	Paolo Cignoni	Restructured to follow extensive comments
11/01/25	V0.5	Paolo Cignoni	Restructured to follow the Steering Committee suggestions
17/01/25	V0.9	Paolo Cignoni	Candidate Version
21/01/25	V1.0	Paolo Cignoni, Léna Czech, Areti Damala	First Version
21/01/25	V1.1	Xavier Rodier	Proofreading

Disclaimer: Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Abstract

The D1.2 Ethics and Data Management Plan (DMP) outlines the strategies for managing data and ensuring ethical compliance throughout the ECHOES project lifecycle. Designed as a living document, it will be updated to reflect the evolving needs and activities of the project.

The DMP focuses on the data generated during the development and implementation of the European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage (ECCCH), ensuring alignment with Open Science and FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable).

Key considerations include:

- FAIR implementation: Ensuring data and metadata are accessible, interoperable, and reusable with persistent identifiers and robust metadata standards.
- Data categorisation: Differentiating between procedural (PD), personal (ID), communication/outreach (OD), coding (CD), and external (ED) data and addressing their specific management needs.
- Data security: Implementing measures such as encryption, two-factor authentication, and regular updates to prevent misuse.
- Ethics and GDPR compliance: Safeguarding personal data and privacy in full accordance with EU regulations.

The DPM underpins the ECHOES's commitment to transparency, sustainability, and collaboration, ensuring that the ECCCH becomes a trusted and enduring platform for the Cultural Heritage community.

Table of Contents

List of abbreviations	5
1. Introduction	6
1.1 Purpose and Scope of the Document	6
1.2 Data Summary.....	6
1.3 ECHOES Data Details.....	7
1.4 Management of ECHOES data	9
2. FAIR data	9
2.1 Findability: Making data easy to locate, including provisions for metadata	9
2.2 Accessibility: Defining the conditions of access to the data	10
2.3 Interoperability: Making data readable, usable, adaptable, and easy to integrate	10
2.4 Re-usability: Fostering data use, re-use, and enrichment.....	11
3. Allocation of resources	11
4. Data security	12
5. Ethics	12
References	13

List of abbreviations

Abb.	
CD	Coding and Implementation Data
DPO	Data Protection Officer
ED	External Data
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
ID	Personal and Individual Data
IP	Intellectual Property
OD	Communication and outreach Data
OSI	Open-Source Initiative
PD	Procedural Data
PID	Persistent Identifier
ROR	Research Organization Registry

1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope of the Document

This document aims to ensure that project activities are conducted in accordance with the principles of research ethics and that the data management performed is compliant with the open science and FAIR principles, with gender equality and non-discrimination, with the Do No Significant Harm principle, and with GDPR requirements.

The ECHOES project aims to establish the European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage (ECCCH). While the ECCCH infrastructure will store significant amounts of CH data, this Data Management Plan (DMP) will specifically address the data generated during the development and implementation of the ECCCH, rather than the diverse cultural heritage data that will be contained within it as detailed in the next sections.

This distinction is present also in the Grant Agreement document; so, this DMP will focus on the data produced by ECHOES and related to building the ECCCH digital ecosystem, and not on the data and metadata that will be stored, processed, or visualised in it.

This document will be updated at M18 to reflect the evolving needs and activities of the project.

1.2 Data Summary

To clarify the concept, in the following we will describe:

- **ECCCH Data:** This refers to the vast and varied cultural heritage data that will be collected, stored, processed, and analysed within the ECCCH platform. This data originates from diverse sources, such as museums, archives, libraries, and research projects, and includes various formats like text, images, 3D models, and audiovisual content. The ECCCH will provide tools and services for managing, accessing, and analysing this data, including features for semantic enrichment, data integration, and collaborative research.
- **ECHOES Data:** This refers to the data generated during the ECHOES project itself, that is specifically related to the development, implementation, and management of the ECCCH infrastructure that we are in charge of implementing. This list is detailed in the next subsection 1.3.

The DMP will outline how this project-specific data will be managed according to FAIR principles, ensuring it is findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. It will specify data formats, metadata standards, storage solutions, and access protocols for this data.

In essence, in a very simplified way, one can think that the ECCCH will act as a digital ecosystem for cultural heritage data, and this DMP focuses on the data produced for building, maintaining and governing this digital ecosystem. The DMP ensures transparency and good data management

practices within the ECHOES project, enabling the ECCCH to function as a reliable and sustainable platform for the long-term preservation and accessibility of cultural heritage.

1.3 ECHOES Data Details

The ECHOES DATA that includes the data and meta-data that we will produce, manage and distribute to build the ECCCH digital ecosystem can be classified as follows:

- a. PROCEDURAL DATA (**PD**): Data (and meta-data) related to implementation procedures and governance structure (e.g., progress reports, procedural protocol, minutes, recommendations and decisions). Some of this type of data is not made public (e.g., board nominations including personal data, see below), reference will be made to the sources.
- b. PERSONAL AND INDIVIDUAL DATA: Data (**ID**) (and meta-data) from individuals. The ECHOES project will collect personal data from the following types of activities:
 - i. Via surveys and questionnaires and/or within the organisation of stakeholder events,
 - ii. By monitoring the activities on the ECCCH infrastructure to assess the quality of the available instruments and software tools,
 - iii. Via user studies for the continuous assessment of the ECCCH infrastructure,
 - iv. By people registering on the web site, to the newsletter(s) and other online activities,
 - v. By capturing and abstracting workflows and best practices,
 - vi. By people registering to the events organised by the project.

The processing and management of this personal data and the protection of privacy in the management of recorded information (audio and/or visual), electronic communications, as well as in public communication networks is in full compliance with General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

- c. EXTERNAL DATA (**ED**): collected background data, like the data, reports, and documents collected from other existing projects. This kind of data collection, like the one carried out in Task 3.1, that focuses on conducting a comprehensive gap analysis to identify existing datasets, tools, and workflows from previous projects that align with the needs of the communities identified in WP4, is crucial to ensure that the ECHOES project builds upon existing work and resources. We will manage this data strictly according to the rights and obligations of the source creator.
- d. IMPLEMENTATION AND CODING DATA (**CD**) Data, code and technical documentation written or adapted for the implementation of the platform, like the one that will be stored on the project or the partners GitHub repository.
- e. COMMUNICATION AND OUTREACH DATA (**OD**): Data (and meta-data) from outreach and communication activities related to the ECHOES project. This type of data includes open

access scientific publications, grey literature publications, policy briefs and reports, project presentations, videos, images, recordings of internal and external events, project website and social media content, newsletters, platform-usage data (metrics from the website and social media). For further information, please refer to deliverable “ECHOES D2.2 Communication Dissemination, Exploitation Plan”.

Using this classification, we can better detail the data concerned by this DMP by considering the data generated, produced, collected and/or managed in the various WPs as follows:

- Project management and coordination documents will be considered PD (WP1 and all WPs);
- Project Communication, Dissemination, Engagement and community building assets, and training materials are classified as OD (WP2, WP5);
- Stakeholders’ collection and analysis of the expectations and needs of the cultural heritage communities for designing the platform (WP3, WP4) like user surveys, and results coming from the participation to focus groups and workshops will be considered ID and ED;
- Technical specifications, design documents, and developer documentation of the ECCCH platform (WP6, WP7, WP8) and the code written or adapted for the implementation of the platform (WP6, WP7, WP8, WP9) will be considered CD; small test datasets to be used for demonstration purposes will also be considered CD and distributed accordingly. Their choice will also be affected by the needs of a liberal distribution;
- Data collected during the process of evaluation and monitoring of the ECCCH infrastructure performance and impact (WP9) will be considered ID;
- Research and development activities related to specific components of the ECCCH, such as the Heritage Digital Twin (HDT) concept and the Knowledge Base (WP7), will be considered PD or OD, while the actual content and structure of the Knowledge Base, that will be one of the key elements of the ECCCH infrastructure, will be considered ECCCH data;
- The implementation of the ECHOES Cascading Grants Programme (WP3), which will fund external projects contributing data and applications to the ECCCH will generate two main class of Data; project proposals, their evaluation and connected activities to the implementation of the grant programme will be considered PD; on the other hand the data produced by the activities of the projects financed by Cascading Grants will be considered ECCCH data if they populate the infrastructure or CD if they contribute with new tools;
- Governance structure setup and long-term management will be considered PD (WP10, WP11).

It should be noted that we are aware of gender bias/issues and that we are committed to avoiding it as much as whenever it is needed like in the generation, management and re-use of data, metadata and other ECHOES outputs. Whenever possible and not needed for reasonable research purpose, gender-disaggregated data are to be collected and analysed.

1.4 Management of ECHOES data

According to the above defined classes of data that we handle during the project, we will manage them as follows:

- a. PROCEDURAL DATA (PD) will be mostly stored and managed using the projects Microsoft Teams-based infrastructure. The accessibility of these documents will depend on the specific type of documents, publications and deliverables. We will rely on the Teams infrastructure for compliance to the common standard;
- b. PERSONAL DATA: Data (ID) will be managed in full compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR); this includes obtaining necessary consent for data use, anonymising data whenever possible, and implementing appropriate security measures to protect personal information;
- c. EXTERNAL DATA (ED): will be managed according to the rights, permissions, obligations, and licensing of the relative source data.
- d. IMPLEMENTATION AND CODING DATA (CD): Data, code and technical documentation written will be released under an OSI accepted open-source licensing scheme to foster the greater reusability and maximum transparency of the implemented infrastructure.
- e. COMMUNICATION AND OUTREACH DATA (OD): The management of this data is discussed in “ECHOES D2.2 Communication Dissemination, Exploitation Plan”.

2. FAIR data

ECHOES will continue to adhere to Open Science Practices and to apply the FAIR Principles to the data and meta-data ensuing from the Project, such commitment was stated in the ex-ante report on the ECCCH and the European Commission’s High-Level Expert Group report of June 2020. In this context, given the interdisciplinary nature of the ECHOES community, particular attention will be placed on the different needs and approaches of the very diverse cultural heritage communities.

2.1 Findability: Making data easy to locate, including provisions for metadata

To guarantee a proper findability of the PD generated by the ECHOES project, we will strive to foster the uptake of Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) for digital objects – including deliverables, materials, data, activities, and events as appropriate and whenever practical within the project. A DOI will be assigned to all the official outputs of the project (e.g., reports, presentations, released tools, deliverables, etc) through Zenodo or other mechanism (e.g., publishing in scientific journals).

In addition, researchers engaged in the ECHOES IP will be asked to foster a comprehensive use of PIDs, but also by registering for an Open Researcher and Contributor ID (ORCID) at individual and appropriate ID such as the Research Organisation Registry (ROR) at the institutional level, if not already done.

2.2 Accessibility: Defining the conditions of access to the data

Following the practices implemented in ECHOES, outputs (PD, OD and CD) will be released as open access documents whenever possible. Accessibility is ensured through a robust data life cycle within the ECHOES project, as the aim is to ultimately make it openly accessible to the wider community through trusted repository (e.g., through Zenodo) or other mechanisms.

Within the Project, services, such as MS Office (including Teams) and GitHub, are exploited for collaborative work and to ensure accessibility of PD/OD and CD documents within the project respectively.

Whenever possible, any scientific contributions or other outputs produced by the project will be made openly available. These will be deposited in open formats in institutional or multi-disciplinary OpenAIRE-compatible repositories, which ensure long-term preservation of the archived items. As a result, they will remain reusable by third parties even after the project concludes.

The ECHOES community is adopting and promoting a collaborative, open, sustainable, responsive and participatory research methodology, and is speeding up the adoption of Open Science practices to improve the robustness, validity, reliability and marketability of its work. In this context, an OpenAIRE “gateway” dedicated to Heritage Science (see <https://heritage-science.openaire.eu/>) is being developed with the aim to collect and improve visibility of the research outputs of the Heritage Science community. In fact, ECHOES will implement the EU Open Access strategy and contribute to shaping the EOSC ecosystem by sharing its accumulated knowledge, tools and data with other existing entities and infrastructures following the paradigm that the data produced for the implementation of the ECCCH will be “as open as possible, as closed as necessary”.

2.3 Interoperability: Making data readable, usable, adaptable, and easy to integrate

All PD, CD, and OD managed within ECHOES will be generated, developed, managed, and stored using standard formats. For PD data, we will follow the guidelines already setup in the D1.1 Project Handbook. All the choices and decisions will be documented and shared in open and accessible platforms. ECHOES aims at attaining interoperability that is both human and machine-readable: formats will be chosen as appropriate to achieve this. The CD generated by the project will adhere to or will use documented open API standards for interaction with other infrastructural components internal and external to the project.

2.4 Re-usability: Fostering data use, re-use, and enrichment

The ECHOES project will work towards optimising data re-use by exploiting an accessible, searchable, open, rich, and well-described meta-data. In this context, both data and meta-data will be released with a defined and documented re-use licence. To ensure that the data is produced in an “as open as possible and as closed as necessary” manner.

If the actual data are embargoed for an agreed period of time, or if certain data-sets are not made public (where appropriate or legally required), these issues shall be clearly documented in the meta-data which may be licensed under an open Creative Commons licence, or an agreed equivalent licence (preferably CC-0 or CC-BY).

To ensure the long-term sustainability of the project documents and materials, the ECHOES project will select a repository which has a well-documented sustainability plan (e.g., Zenodo “ECCCH” Community).

3. Allocation of resources

Responsibility for ensuring that ECHOES data and meta-data is compliant with the FAIR Principles will rest primarily with the Project Coordinating Institution. The Steering Committee of ECHOES will be consulted in case this DMP has to be revised and updated according to project specifications and development. The project will nominate a Data Protection Officer (DPO), who will be responsible for ensuring that the processing of personal data complies with data protection rules. The DPO will review the processes used in the project to handle the various classes of data and ensure that they align with the project's Data Management Plan (DMP).

4. Data security

Management of data and meta-data will remain the responsibility of ECHOES participating content providers. For all classes of data, we will follow best practices to ensure the integrity of such objects is secure from accidental misuse or malicious tampering, and we will ensure that personal data is protected according to EU regulations, including the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (see below). Towards preventing misusing of data and metadata, the ECHOES project will implement:

- Two-factor authentication for infrastructure administration tasks,
- Application of PID for identification of providers and users of data and meta-data,
- Ensure any stored passwords are hashed with modern cryptographic algorithms,
- Frequently update IT resources to ensure that they run the latest security patches and that they will allow for components to be rapidly and reliably redeployed in the event of a security breach.
- Data designed as sensitive will not be allowed to store on local devices, such as laptops or desktop systems. It may only be stored on servers and services that have been approved to meet the necessary requirements

5. Ethics

The ECHOES community is fully committed to the principles of responsible science that include research ethics, data management compliance with the Open Science and FAIR principles, gender equality and non-discrimination, and the implementation of GDPR requirements. The operationalisation of the ECHOES project is not expected to raise any particular ethical issues; however, the ECHOES Steering Committee will always control and guarantee that all collected and processed personal data is treated following the ethics provisions set out in the Grant Agreement, and notably the highest ethical standards and the applicable international, EU and national laws. Approval from local and national authorities in charge of data protection will be secured, wherever necessary. Personal data that will be collected on questionnaires for user and provider evaluation and event's organisation, the processing of personal data and the protection of privacy in recorded information (audio and/or visual) and electronic communications, as well as in public communication networks will fully comply with General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC. Finally, ECHOES fully complies with the “do not significant harm” principle as per Art. 17 of Regulation (EU) No 2020/852. A “Privacy and Cookies policy” - already in place in the framework of the ECHOES community - will be fine-tuned accordingly.

The implications of application of current and upcoming Artificial Intelligence technologies to the ECCCH data are discussed in a series of deliverables of the WP12 of the project that face these issues explicitly, namely D12.1 and D12.2.

References

Brunet, Pere, Livio de Luca, Eero Hyvönen, Adeline Joffres, Peter Plassmayer, Martijn Pronk, Roberto Scopigno, and Gabor Sonkoly. "Report on a European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage." (2022).